

The role of pharmacists in asthma management: patient opinions and expectations in North Macedonia

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess patients' perceptions of inhaler technique education and the pharmacist's role in asthma care in North Macedonia. A cross-sectional survey was conducted from July to September 2024 at the University Clinic for Pulmonology and Allergology in Skopje, involving 187 adult asthma patients. Most participants (69%) reported adherence to therapy, but 13.9% had never received inhaler training, and only 27.3% had been instructed by a pharmacist. While 96.3% expressed interest in pharmacist counseling on medications, only 48.7% were open to pharmacist-led inhaler training. Significant associations were found between adherence and both gender ($p = 0.040$) and inhaler training. These findings suggest limited awareness of the pharmacist's clinical role. Expanding pharmacist-led education in community pharmacies and fostering collaboration with physicians could improve asthma outcomes and promote more effective use of healthcare resources.

Keywords

pharmacist, education, patient opinion, asthma, community pharmacy

Introduction

Community pharmacies have evolved beyond dispensing medicines. In recent decades, pharmacists' positions and responsibilities in the healthcare system have significantly changed and expanded to address patients' needs (Hepler and Strand 1990; van Mil and Schulz 2006; Wledenmayer et al. 2006; Urlick and Meggs 2019). Extended waiting times for physician appointments lead many patients to turn to pharmacists, who offer readily accessible expertise

and prompt support. Consequently, patients interact with pharmacists more frequently than with general practitioners (Tsuyuki et al. 2018). Moreover, as easily accessible healthcare providers, skilled and knowledgeable pharmacists are well positioned to play a crucial role in patients' chronic disease management. The World Health Organization highlights the vital role of community pharmacists in chronic disease management by improving medication understanding, health-related quality of life, and self-management (WHO 2011). Similarly, the International Phar-

maceutical Federation advocates for pharmaceutical care, actively empowering pharmacists to support patients with chronic conditions (FIP 2005). Nevertheless, in North Macedonia, pharmacists are still not fully recognized as healthcare professionals capable of playing a significant role in managing chronic diseases. The existing legislation in North Macedonia remains primarily focused on a product-oriented approach to pharmaceutical practice, with limited emphasis on patient care (Ivanovska 2011; Patcheva et al. 2012). This situation highlights the need for legislative reforms in North Macedonia to align pharmacy practice with European Union standards. Such reforms should correspond to the needs of the national health system, aiming to enhance overall health outcomes while improving accessibility and efficiency (Patcheva et al. 2012). Standardized pharmaceutical service programs are essential to guarantee equal access to high-quality health education and guidance for all patients. In many low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), community pharmacists ensure a steady supply of essential medications and provide support for managing chronic conditions such as cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), diabetes, asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and mental illness through their expertise and accessibility (George et al. 2010). Implementing standardized pharmaceutical service programs can improve patient care and significantly reduce overall national healthcare costs (Malet-Larrea et al. 2016).

Asthma is a chronic respiratory disease that can significantly impact patients, their families, and society (Reddel et al. 2022). It causes shortness of breath, wheezing, and flare-ups, which can lead to activity limitations, emergency medical visits, or even life-threatening situations. Proper asthma management depends on medication adherence, environmental control, and, most importantly, correct inhaler technique. Incorrect use of inhalers is a major cause of poor asthma control and treatment failure. Ensuring proper inhaler use is therefore crucial for effective symptom management (Price et al. 2013; Volerman et al. 2019). Despite the importance of proper inhaler technique, many healthcare providers fail to educate patients on correct use (Fink and Rubin 2005). Studies have shown that pharmacist-led interventions in community pharmacies can significantly improve asthma management and patient outcomes (Mehuys et al. 2008). This approach should be adopted as standard practice in healthcare systems across North Macedonia and other developing countries. To enhance these services, it is essential to understand patients' knowledge, expectations, and perceptions regarding the additional support they can receive from pharmacists, particularly in managing conditions such as asthma. Consequently, this study assesses patients' experiences and perceptions regarding inhaler technique education and pharmaceutical care in asthma management. By evaluating patients' awareness of proper inhaler use, adherence to prescribed therapy, sources of prior training, and their interest in pharmacist-led education, this study seeks to identify gaps in asthma management and highlight the potential role of community pharmacists in improving patient outcomes in North Macedonia.

Materials and methods

Study design

This study was conducted at the Public Health Institution (PHI) University Clinic for Pulmonology and Allergology – Skopje from July to September 2024 in North Macedonia, using an author-designed questionnaire. The study group included patients with chronic asthma who visited a pulmonologist and used inhalers. The inclusion criteria for this study were patients aged 18 years or older with a confirmed clinical diagnosis of chronic asthma, verified by a specialist pulmonologist based on medical records and clinical evaluation, who voluntarily consented to participate. Exclusion criteria included lack of informed consent, withdrawal from participation, or any condition that prevented effective communication with the patient. A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed, of which 187 were completed and returned, resulting in a response rate of 93.5%.

The Ethical Committee at the Faculty of Medical Sciences, Goce Delcev University – Stip, North Macedonia, approved the study (Doc. No. 2005-137/4). All respondents signed an informed consent statement before participating in the study. Prior to completing the questionnaire, participants were informed about the study's purpose, anonymity, and scientific intent. A private space was provided to ensure their comfort while answering the questionnaire. The survey consisted of 12 carefully designed questions, combining closed-ended and semi-open formats. The initial section of the questionnaire collected general demographic and clinical information, including gender, age, education level, employment status, and duration of asthma. Subsequent questions addressed prescribed therapy, adherence to therapy, and inhaler technique, including whether patients had received instruction on proper inhaler use and the source of that instruction (pharmacist or physician). Furthermore, participants were invited to share their opinions and interests in pharmaceutical care for asthma, including pharmacist-led education on inhaler technique and the 'New Drug' service.

Statistical analysis

The obtained data were tabulated using Microsoft Excel® (Microsoft Corp., Redmond, WA, USA), cleaned, and subsequently analyzed using the statistical software Jamovi (version 2.6, retrieved from <https://www.jamovi.org>) (Meyer et al. 2023; Jamovi 2024; R Core Team 2024).

Results

Participants' characteristics

The study included a diverse group of patients with varying demographic and clinical backgrounds. A total of 187 patients participated in the survey, with ages ranging from 19 to 82 years (mean age: 50.16 ± 13.49 years). A comprehensive overview of their demographic, clinical, and therapy-related characteristics is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic, clinical, and therapy-related characteristics of study participants.

Item	Category	Percentage (%)	95% CI (%)
Gender	Male	62.6	55.7–69.5
	Female	37.4	30.5–44.3
Education	Primary school	17.6	12.1–23.1
	High school	46.5	39.4–53.6
	College	2.7	0.4–5.0
	University education	33.2	26.5–39.9
Smoking status	Yes	50.8	43.6–58.0
	No	49.2	42.0–56.4
Disease Duration	Less than 1 year	18.2	12.7–23.7
	Between 1–5 years	69.5	62.9–76.1
	Between 5–20 years or more	12.3	7.6–17.0
Treatment	ICS+LABA	78	72.1–83.9
	LAMA	6.4	2.9–9.9
	ICS+LAMA+LABA	9.1	5.0–13.2
	ICS	6.4	2.9–9.9
Inhaler training	By physician	58.8	51.7–65.9
	By pharmacist	27.3	20.9–33.7
	None	13.9	8.9–18.9
Training using demo inhaler	By physician	49.7	42.5–56.9
	By pharmacist	5.9	2.5–9.3
	None	44.4	37.3–51.5
Adherence to prescribed therapy	Yes	69	62.4–75.6
	No	16.6	11.3–21.9
	Sometimes	14.4	9.4–19.4

*ICS+LABA= Inhaled Corticosteroid + Long-Acting Beta-2 Agonist; LAMA = Long-Acting Muscarinic Antagonist; ICS + LAMA + LABA = Inhaled Corticosteroid + Long-Acting Muscarinic Antagonist + Long-Acting Beta-2 Agonist; ICS = Inhaled Corticosteroid, CI – confidence interval.

Based on the data in Table 1, the study sample consists predominantly of male participants (62.6%), with a lower proportion of females (37.4%). Regarding educational background, the majority had a high school education (46.5%), followed by university education (33.2%), while a smaller percentage had only primary education (17.6%) or college degrees (2.7%). Smoking status was evenly distributed, with 50.8% identifying as smokers and 49.2% as non-smokers, which may have implications for disease progression and treatment effectiveness. Most participants had been diagnosed with the disease for 1 to 5 years (69.5%), with fewer cases diagnosed less than a year ago (18.2%) or persisting for over 5 years (12.3%). In terms of therapy, the most commonly used inhaler was the pressurized metered-dose inhaler (pMDI) (56.1%). Training on inhaler use was primarily provided by physicians (58.8%), while pharmacists contributed to 27.3% of training sessions. However, 13.9% of participants reported that they had not received any training. Regarding training using a demonstration inhaler, a significant 44.4% did not receive any practical demonstration. Most training sessions were provided by physicians (49.7%), and only 5.9% were delivered by pharmacists (Fig. 1).

The data indicate that adherence to prescribed therapy is relatively high, with 69% of participants fully adhering to their prescribed regimen, while 14.4% adhered intermittently, and 16.6% did not adhere at all.

Patients' opinions on pharmaceutical care services

When respondents were asked whether they would like the pharmacist to provide information about newly prescribed medications, an overwhelming 96.3% responded positively, indicating a strong preference for pharmacist involvement in medication counseling. Only 3.7% declined this service. However, when questioned about receiving inhalation training from a pharmacist at a community pharmacy, the responses were more divided. While 48.7% expressed willingness, a slightly higher percentage (51.3%) were not in favor of receiving such training from a pharmacist.

Crosstabulation of the data revealed statistically significant associations (Chi-squared test [χ^2], $p < 0.05$) between several variables (Table 2). Specifically, adherence to prescribed therapy was significantly related to gender as well as to inhaler training. Additionally, a significant association was found between participants' willingness to receive pharmacist-provided information about newly prescribed medication and their interest in receiving inhalation training from a pharmacist at a community pharmacy. In detail, the contingency table examining the relationship between gender and therapy adherence indicated that among females ($n = 70$), 44 reported full adherence, 16 reported partial adherence, and 10 reported no adherence. In contrast, among males ($n = 117$), 85 reported full

Figure 1. Demo education for the use of inhalers.

Table 2. Statistical results for contingency tables.

Statistics	Therapy adherence vs Gender	Therapy adherence vs inhaler training	Pharmacist inhalation training vs new medication info
Sample size (N)	187	187	187
Degrees of freedom (df)	2	4	1
Chi-squared value	6.46	20	7.67
Chi-squared p-value	0.04	< 0.001	0.006
Likelihood ratio value	6.24	16.4	10.4
Likelihood ratio p-value	0.044	0.003	0.001
Fisher's exact test p-value	0.047	0.002	0.006
Phi-coefficient value	/	/	0.203
Cramer's V value	0.186	0.231	0.203

adherence, 11 reported partial adherence, and 21 reported no adherence (Fig. 2). The results of the Chi-squared test ($\chi^2 = 6.46$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.040$) reveal a statistically significant relationship between gender and therapy adherence, suggesting that adherence may vary by gender. This finding is further supported by the likelihood ratio test ($p = 0.044$) and Fisher's exact test ($p = 0.047$), both of which confirm a significant association. The Cramer's V value of 0.186 indicates a small effect size, suggesting a moderate association between gender and therapy adherence. While the relationship is statistically significant, it is not overwhelmingly strong. The analysis shows that therapy adherence is significantly associated with gender, with females exhibiting a slightly higher rate of full adherence (44 out of 70) compared to males (85 out of 117). However, the difference in adherence levels between genders is relatively modest, as both groups display similar trends, with the majority of participants reporting full adherence to therapy. The small effect size (Cramer's V = 0.186) suggests that other factors beyond gender likely contribute to therapy adherence (Table 2).

The contingency table examining the relationship between inhaler training and therapy adherence reveals important insights (Table 2). Of the 51 participants who received training from a pharmacist, 8 reported no adherence, 8 reported partial adherence, and 35 reported full adherence. Among the 110 participants who received training from a physician, 11 reported no adherence, 17 reported partial adherence, and 82 reported full adherence. For the 26 participants who did not receive any training, 12 reported no adherence, 2 reported partial adherence, and 12 reported full adherence (Fig. 3).

The results of the Chi-squared test ($\chi^2 = 20.0$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the type of inhaler training (by pharmacist, physician, or none) is linked to varying levels of adherence. The likelihood ratio test also yielded a significant result ($p = 0.003$), reinforcing the Chi-squared findings. Additionally, Fisher's exact test confirmed the significance of this association ($p = 0.002$), suggesting that the observed relationship is unlikely due to random chance. The Cramer's V value of

Figure 2. Relationship between gender and adherence to prescribed therapy.

Figure 3. Relationship between inhaler training and adherence to prescribed therapy.

0.231 indicates a moderate effect size, signifying a meaningful, though not strong, relationship between inhaler training and therapy adherence. The analysis demonstrates that inhaler training significantly impacts therapy adherence. Participants who received training from either a pharmacist or a physician exhibited higher adherence levels compared to those who did not receive any training. Notably, full adherence was observed in 82 out of 110 participants (74.6%) who received inhaler technique training from a physician and 35 out of 51 participants (68.6%) trained by a pharmacist. Even among those who received no training, a level of adherence was observed, although the numbers were lower (12 out of 26 participants, 46.2%). These results underscore the importance of inhaler training – particularly from healthcare professionals such as pharmacists and physicians – in improving therapy adherence. While the moderate effect size (Cramer’s $V = 0.231$) suggests that other factors may also influence adherence,

the findings highlight the value of structured patient education in enhancing treatment outcomes.

The contingency table examining the relationship between participants’ willingness to receive pharmacist-provided information about a newly prescribed medication and their interest in receiving inhalation training from a pharmacist in a community pharmacy revealed that among the 91 participants willing to receive inhalation training, 84 also expressed interest in receiving medication information from the pharmacist, while 7 were not willing. Conversely, among the 96 participants not willing to receive inhalation training, all expressed interest in receiving medication information from a pharmacist (Fig. 4).

The results from the Chi-squared test (χ^2) indicate a statistically significant association between willingness to receive pharmacist-provided information about a newly prescribed medication and willingness to receive inhalation training ($\chi^2 = 7.67, df = 1, p = 0.006$). This suggests that par-

Figure 4. Patient willingness to receive pharmacist-provided information about a newly prescribed medication and their interest in receiving inhalation training from a pharmacist.

ticipants who are open to one form of pharmacist-led support (either medication information or inhalation training) are more likely to be receptive to the other. The likelihood ratio test further supports this finding ($p = 0.001$), and Fisher's exact test also confirms the association ($p = 0.006$), indicating that the relationship is unlikely due to chance. The Phi coefficient and Cramer's V values of 0.203 indicate a moderate effect size, suggesting a meaningful, though not particularly strong, relationship between the two variables. This statistically significant association highlights the potential for integrated patient education within community pharmacies. Participants who are willing to engage with one form of pharmacist intervention (such as medication information) are also likely to engage with other forms of support, such as inhalation training. The moderate effect size (Cramer's V = 0.203) implies that, while a notable relationship exists, other factors may also influence participants' willingness to engage with pharmacists (Table 2).

Discussion

The Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA) and the World Health Organization (WHO) emphasize that correct inhaler use and adherence to treatment instructions are essential for controlling asthma (GINA 2020; WHO 2024). Given the central role of adherence and proper inhaler technique in managing the disease, these results underscore the importance of educating patients and promoting consistency in inhaler devices. Pharmacists play a critical role within asthma care teams, with a primary responsibility centered on providing comprehensive education about dispensed medications, particularly the correct use of inhalers (Bridgeman and Wilken 2021). Despite this, the survey findings indicated that this role was predominantly undertaken by physicians. The limited involvement

of pharmacists may result from time constraints during medication dispensing, highlighting the need to reorganize work activities to better align with pharmacists' professional competencies. Contributing factors may also include the need for further education and training of pharmacists to deliver these services, as well as the necessity of clearly defining and regulating such services within a legal framework. This gap is particularly concerning given the strong evidence supporting the effectiveness of pharmacist-led education in improving inhaler technique and overall disease management. For example, a prospective observational study demonstrated that pharmacist intervention increased the rate of correct inhaler use from 24% to 79%, alongside measurable improvements in asthma control and medication adherence (Giraud and Allaert 2011). Furthermore, a randomized controlled trial found that even a brief, two-minute session with a pharmacist was more effective than written or video-based methods in achieving correct inhaler technique (Axtell et al. 2017). These findings underscore the pivotal role that pharmacists can play in patient education and highlight the pressing need to expand their involvement in improving inhaler technique in patients with asthma, both in clinical and community pharmacy settings. Implementing strategies to increase patient education and inhaler training, particularly in community pharmacies, could lead to significant improvements in adherence and overall health outcomes.

According to the findings, a strong majority of participants (96.3%) indicated a willingness to receive information from pharmacists regarding newly prescribed medications, underscoring the value patients place on pharmacist involvement in medication counseling. However, the lower acceptance rate for inhalation training in community pharmacies may reflect a preference for physician-led instruction, a lack of awareness of pharmacists' expertise in inhaler technique, or potential concerns

about the quality and accessibility of such training. These insights emphasize the need for improved communication regarding the pharmacist's role in inhaler education and the implementation of strategies to increase patient confidence in pharmacist-led inhalation training.

A statistically significant association between gender and adherence to prescribed therapy was observed, suggesting that gender may influence adherence. This also implies that additional factors contribute to adherence behaviors and should be further explored in future research. The literature presents mixed results regarding the influence of gender. For instance, Boucquemont et al. (2019) reported that gender differences in medication adherence vary with age: no significant differences were observed among younger adolescents, whereas young women tended to adhere more consistently to treatment than young men. In contrast, a study by Chen et al. (2014) found that male patients with hypertension demonstrated higher adherence levels compared to female patients, highlighting the presence of gender-specific factors influencing adherence. These contrasting findings underscore the complexity of the relationship between gender and medication adherence, indicating the need for more nuanced and context-specific research. A significant association was also found between the willingness to receive pharmacist-provided medication information and inhaler training, suggesting that patients open to one type of pharmacist support are likely to accept other forms as well. A recent review by Nikolov and Petrova (2025) highlighted various technological innovations designed to support patients in maintaining their medication regimens and improving adherence. These include electronic monitoring devices (EMDs), mobile applications, web-based platforms, and smart inhalers equipped with sensors that track usage and provide real-time feedback. These technologies can enhance adherence and should be considered in future strategies (Nikolov and Petrova 2025).

Studies worldwide have shown that pharmacist-led education helps patients better understand their treatment and adhere to it, as pharmacists are among the most accessible healthcare providers (Kovačević et al. 2018; Jia et al. 2020; Putman et al. 2022). A randomized controlled trial conducted in Italy demonstrated the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of the Italian medicines use review (I-MUR) service for asthma patients, the country's first cognitive pharmaceutical service. Following the success of this service, the Italian Ministry of Health endorsed a shift in community pharmacy practice, leading to the implementation of I-MUR as the first nationally funded cognitive pharmaceutical service in Italy. This initiative underscores the increasing recognition of pharmacists' pivotal role in improving medication adherence and providing patient education (Manfrin et al. 2017). The success of I-MUR can serve as a valuable model for expanding similar services in North Macedonia, potentially improving asthma care and enhancing patient outcomes.

Community pharmacies are uniquely positioned to offer comprehensive care by integrating inhaler training with medication counseling. By addressing these critical

aspects together, pharmacists not only enhance patient adherence but also improve therapeutic outcomes, fostering a more holistic approach to asthma care. To address this, a comprehensive education and training initiative in North Macedonia was launched in 2023, with support from the International Primary Care Respiratory Group (IPCRG) and the Center for Family Medicine at the Medical Faculty, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, Republic of North Macedonia. The program focused on "train the trainers" sessions for family physicians, nurses, and community pharmacists, aiming to enhance asthma care across the country. In early 2023, 16 pharmacists and five family physicians were trained to conduct workshops using an academic training program. This led to the successful implementation of 20 regional education workshops, involving 400 community pharmacists in the national asthma care strategy (Naumovska et al. 2024). Although this initiative is in its early stages, it offers a promising model upon which a broader strategy for successful asthma management can be built, ultimately improving adherence to therapy among asthma patients in North Macedonia.

Conclusion

This study highlights the role of healthcare professionals – pharmacists and physicians – in supporting improved therapy adherence among patients with asthma. Significant associations were found between therapy adherence and both gender and the type of inhaler training received. Although patients showed strong interest in receiving information about medications from pharmacists, their willingness to receive training on the correct use of inhalers was more limited. These results indicate a lack of awareness among patients regarding pharmacists' expertise in this area. Introducing specialized patient education programs within community pharmacies would enhance the pharmacist's role in contributing to improved health outcomes and optimizing the utilization of healthcare resources. Strengthening collaboration between pharmacists and physicians, alongside increasing public awareness of pharmacists' clinical competencies, will be key to advancing patient-centered asthma care.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: This study was conducted at Public Health Institution (PHI) University Clinic for Pulmonology and Allergology – Skopje, North Macedonia

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

All authors contributed to the study design and manuscript preparation. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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